

Location–Allocation of Waste Bins in the University of Ibadan

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Abstract

Effective management of solid waste requires proper allocation of waste bins for waste collection. Developing countries, particularly Nigeria, face a shortage of properly located waste bins. This results in improper disposal of solid waste, littering the environment with solid waste. To enhance solid waste management, bins must be optimally located to prevent indiscriminate disposal and environmental littering. The study applied a location set covering problem model to define and solve the location and allocation of waste bins within the University of Ibadan, Ibadan. A Geographic Information System was used to analyse the spatial distribution of potential waste bin locations, and the distances between them were determined for different zones in the university. The model locates 2, 4, 1, 4, 7, 8, 2, and 2 waste bins in zones 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8, respectively, ensuring every waste generation point is covered within a predefined maximal service distance. The study determines the optimal number of waste bins required to serve a given set of waste generation points within the 8 zones of the university, ensuring proper waste disposal and a safe environment. This study supports efficient waste bin placement to ensure adequate service coverage and promote a culture of proper waste disposal across the university.

Keywords: Solid Waste; Location-Allocation; Covering models; Waste bins

INTRODUCTION

Municipal solid waste management (MSW) has become a major environmental challenge worldwide (Giusti, 2009; Dawar *et al.*, 2025). A report by The World Bank shows that the world generates 2.01 billion tonnes of MSW annually. Nigeria is estimated to generate around 32 million tonnes annually while only 30% of the waste generated is efficiently collected and disposed of (The World Bank, 2018; Agbo Jr, 2023). Due to the continuous growth and urbanization in developing countries in Africa, Nigeria in particular, the waste generation rate has increased, leading to the environmental degradation caused by inefficient management of solid waste (Onibokun, 1999; Kusi-Appiah *et al.*, 2025). Further research shows that approximately 5.2 million people in developing countries also die yearly of solid waste-related diseases (Meyers *et al.*, 2006; Chakraborty *et al.*, 2025)

Location-allocation models have been widely used for solving decision problems involving facility siting (Manzini & Gebennini, 2008; Wang *et al.*, 2018; Murray *et al.*, 2020; Dawar *et al.*, 2025).

It has been applied in the food service industry (Bindi *et al.*, 2008; Chen *et al.*, 2024), routing decisions and supply chain (Lashine *et al.* 2006; Cao *et al.* 2021; Arevalo-Ascanio *et al.* 2024), inventory problem (Mousavi *et al.*, 2015; Das *et al.*, 2023; Camacho-Vallejo *et al.*, 2024), transportation systems (Hamadani *et al.*, 2013; Yang *et al.*, 2024)), healthcare (Syam & Cote, 2010; Salami *et al.*, 2023; Okunade *et al.* 2025), and waste management (Purkayastha *et al.*, 2015; Leuveano *et al.*, 2024). Location allocation models have been applied to solid waste management (Bhat, 1996; Hemmelmayr *et al.*, 2014; Habibi *et al.*, 2017; Kituku *et al.*, 2020; Sadati *et al.* 2024).

Church (2002) described the geographic information system (GIS) as an important tool in the effective and efficient location of facilities. It has been used to accurately determine the type and sizes of waste bins and best possible locations at minimum cost (Vijay *et al.* 2005; Zamorano *et al.*, 2009; Chandio, 2013; Terzi *et al.*, 2025). GIS and Linear Programming (LP) were used to develop a location-allocation model for enhancing municipal waste collection efficiency showing how the spatial visualization of LP solutions could be augmented through GIS (Ghiani *et al.*, 2012; Rathore *et al.*, 2020; Singhal & Goel, 2022; Khan *et al.*, 2024).

Universities are hubs of diverse activities, ranging from classrooms and laboratories to outdoor events and recreational spaces each contributing to distinct patterns of waste generation, wide array of waste types with fluctuations based on the academic calendar and specific campus events. The efficacy of waste management systems directly influences the overall environmental impact and sustainability goals of Universities (Alshuwaikhat & Abubakar, 2008; Giurea *et al.*, 2024). Several studies have been carried out on waste management systems in universities (Ebrahim *et al.*, 2017; Anh Khoa *et al.*, 2020; Longo *et al.*, 2021; Otton *et al.*, 2022; Giurea *et al.*, 2024). However, information on waste management in Nigerian universities is sparse in the literature. This study, therefore, seeks to minimise the total number of waste bins to be located, chosen from a set of potential locations.

METHODOLOGY

This section presents the mathematical model formulation, the investigated case, and solution procedure.

Mathematical Model Formulation

This section outlines the model assumptions, notations, and formulation used to determine the optimal number and placement of waste bins.

Model Assumptions

The model assumes all parameters remain constant during the planning horizon. Each waste generation point is considered covered if it lies within a predefined maximum distance from a waste bin. The coverage distance is assumed to be the same for all demand locations. All bins have equal capacity, sufficient to handle the assigned waste.

Model Notations

i - index of waste generation points $i=1,2, 3, \dots, N$

j - index of potential waste bin locations $j= 1,2, 3, \dots, M$

d_{ij} - distance between waste generation point i and waste bin at location j

D - coverage distance

g_i - waste generated at point i

c_j - capacity of waste bin at location j

z_{ij} - waste generation points i covered by waste bin at location j

y_{ij} – waste generation points i assigned to waste bin at location j and it is defined as

$$y_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if waste generation points } i \text{ is assigned to waste bin at location } j \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

x_j - number of waste bin at location j and it is defined as

$$x_j = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if a waste bin is located at location } j \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Location Set Covering Problem (LSCP)

Location set-covering problem model for the optimal location of waste bins is

Minimise

$$Z = \sum_{j=1}^M x_j \quad (1)$$

Subject to

$$\sum_{j=1}^M z_{ij} x_j \geq 1 \quad \forall i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N g_i y_{ij} \leq c_j \quad \forall j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, M \quad (3)$$

$$x_j = 0, 1 \text{ for } j = 1, 2, \dots, M \quad (4)$$

$$y_{ij} = 0, 1 \text{ for } \forall i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N, \forall j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, M \quad (5)$$

Equation (1) is the objective function, and it minimises the number of waste bins to cover all waste generation points. Equation (2) states that waste generation point i can be covered by waste bin at location j , if the distance is within the coverage distance. Equation (3) states that the total waste generated from all generation points i assigned to a waste bin located at j must not exceed capacity of the waste bin and equations (4) to (5) give the integer constraints.

Investigated Case and Data Collection

The study area is University of Ibadan, Nigeria, which occupies 1,032 hectares and accommodates over 33,000 students. To enhance waste management, optimal placement of waste bins is essential to meet demand across all waste generation points. Data was sourced from the Physical Planning Unit. ArcGIS was used to determine the centroid of each zone and potential locations in each zone for placement of waste bins. Coordinates of each potential waste bin location were taken using GPS. Map in Figure 1 and various distances between locations in all the 8 zones were determined with the help of Geographic Information Processing (GIS), but for paucity of space, Table 1 gives the distances between locations for zone 1. Figure 1 shows the university map with zones and their centroids. Daily waste generation was estimated using secondary data from Bamgboye *et al.* (2021), which provided daily average MSW generation rate for University of Ibadan as follows: 1.55 kg/household/day, and 0.245 kg/head/day in the staff residential areas and students' halls of residence respectively. It was 46.83 kg/faculty/day and 0.415 kg /shop/day in the academic and business areas respectively. The MSW generation rate were used with spatial information from physical planning unit to determine the waste generated per day in each zone. Table 2 gives the number of potential waste bin location sites and daily waste generated for each zone in the university. There were a total of 79 potential waste bin locations across the university, and the waste generation points were grouped into eight zones, comprising both academic and non-academic areas. Based on the volume of waste estimated per day per each zone, the capacity of waste bin used in solving the LSCP model was 500 litres. Coverage distance of 200 m was used based on the equity of service consideration by Tralhão *et al.* (2010) that ensures service distance should not be more than 200 m. The data obtained were defined as variables and parameters for the LSCP model, and the covering-based model was solved using Lingo 18.0 software.

Figure 1: Map of University of Ibadan showing each zone and their centroids

Table 1: Distances between locations for Zone 1 (in metres)

Zone	Types of Area	Number Potentials Locations	of Waste generated/day (kg)
1	Non-Academic	8	111.60
2	Academic	8	93.66
3	Academic	4	46.83
4	Academic	11	187.32
5	Non-Academic	22	215.45
6	Non-Academic	15	2742.36
7	Academic	6	46.83
8	Non-Academic	5	69.75

Table 2: Zones, and their number of

potentials locations and waste generated per day in each zone

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1	-	210	200	220	350	450	300	600
2	210	-	230	170	260	290	400	500
3	200	230	-	60	140	300	170	450
4	220	170	60	-	110	270	200	400
5	350	260	140	110	-	180	200	350
6	450	290	300	270	180	-	400	170
7	300	400	170	200	200	400	-	500
8	600	500	450	400	350	170	500	-

2.3

Problem Solution Procedure

The solution procedure for LSCP for the optimal location of waste bins is given as follows:

Step 1: Obtain the parameters $\{M, D, d_{ij}, g_i, \text{ and } c_j, \}$ for each zone from the data gotten from the case study

Step 2: Determine the distance between waste generation points and waste bin location, d_{ij} using GIS for each zone.

Step 3: Set up the tableau to compute z_{ij} , for each zone, which is defined as follows:

$$z_{ij} = \{1, \text{ if } d_{ij} \leq D \text{ } 0, \text{ otherwise} \quad (6)$$

Step 4: Define the variables and parameters as LSCP for each zone.

Step 5: Solve the LSCP using Lingo 18.0 software to obtain the values of an optimal number of waste bins, x_j to cover all the locations in each zone.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 3 gives 8 potential locations to site the waste bins in zone 1 and their coverage distance of 200 m as expressed by Equation (6). The optimal number of waste bins determined by LSCP using Lingo 18.0 software is 2 sited at locations 4 and 6 in zone 1. Locations 4 and 6 were selected as optimum waste bin locations from which distances to other locations within the zone must not exceed maximum coverage distance, D equals 200 m. Also, Table 4 gives the number of waste bins located and the respective location in each zone. As observed from the covering tableau, some distances between locations for siting of waste bins were greater than the set maximum distance, and they were not considered. For example, in Table 1, distances between location 1 and location 4, location 1 and location 5 is given as 220 m and 350 m, respectively were assigned “0” in Table 3 because they exceeded 200 m, which is set as the maximum distance, D . Also, attached to Table 3 is the results of the optimal locations of waste bins for Zone 1, the solver assigns “1” to locations which serve as optimum points for locating waste bins and “0” to signify locations where waste bins cannot be located. The results shows that locations 4 and 6 were picked as location to site waste bins in Zone 1.

Table 3: Covering problem Tableau and results obtained for the optimal location of waste bin in Zone 1

Coverage Tableau									Optimum location
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	
1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
3	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
4	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
5	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
6	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1
7	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
8	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0

Table 4 gives the optimal number of waste bins in each zone and their locations. The LSCP model locates 2, 4, 1, 4, 7, 8, 2, and 2 waste bins in zones 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8, respectively, ensuring every waste generation point is covered within a predefined maximal service distance. Zones 5 and 6 have the highest number of waste bins because they comprise residential areas and students’ hall of residences where the bulk of the waste is generated.

Table 4: Number of waste bins located in each zone and their corresponding locations

Zone	Type of Area	Optimal number of waste bins	Location within the zone
1	Non-Academic	2	4,6
2	Academic	4	1,3,6,7
3	Academic	1	2
4	Academic	4	3,6,9,11

5	Non-Academic	7	3,5,8,10,13,18,20
6	Non-Academic	8	2,3,4,5,6,12,14,15
7	Academic	2	1,5
8	Non-Academic	2	1,3

As shown in Table 4, the total number of waste bins 500 litres the four academic zones contain a total of 11 waste bins, while the four non-academic zones contain 19 bins. This suggests that the volume of waste generated in non-academic area which comprises of residential areas and students' hall of residences are higher than that of academic areas. Location of waste bins where every household within the zones can easily access them has the advantage of improving the waste collection efficiency by minimising the distance travelled to dispose of the solid waste. This implies that from any point within the zones, the maximum walk to any of the locations where waste bins are sited is 200 m. Sensitivity analysis of different coverage distances showed that an increase in coverage distance reduces the number of waste bins to be sited, as corroborated by Di Felice (2014) as cited in Purkayastha *et al.* (2015). When coverage distance is smaller, compliance to proper disposal of waste is improved but the cost of infrastructure is increased. There is need to find an optimum coverage distance that will balance the trade-off between compliance and cost. Also, optimal location of waste bins improves accessibility to dispose waste as frequent as possible, and this in a way encourages the use of waste bins thus ensuring cleanliness of the environment and promotes the culture of cleanliness as well. Operational efficiency is improved, when waste bins are optimally located and this also impact the costs of transportation, equipment and manpower.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Optimal location and allocation of waste bins in the Universities for proper disposal of waste is essential to achieving the sustainability goals. This study used a location set covering problem model and GIS techniques to determine waste bin locations across eight zones within the university. The optimal solution placed 2, 4, 1, 4, 7, 8, 2, and 2 waste bins in zones 1 to 8, respectively, ensuring all waste generation points are within a defined service distance. The study gives an optimal location and allocation of waste bins to maximise coverage in all waste generation points. These findings highlight the importance of effective planning and allocation of waste bins that encourages good culture on waste disposal as well support an efficient and smooth waste management operations in Universities.

While the model promotes efficient waste disposal, it relies on secondary data for waste estimates, which should be periodically updated to reflect infrastructural and population changes. Also, further studies should consider the use of smart technology to integrate real-time monitoring systems that monitor the fill level of waste bins and automatically trigger collection actions, thereby reducing waste overflow and ensuring a clean environment. Further studies should also consider vehicle routing for transfer of waste from collection points to dumpsite and multi-objectives optimisation models that considers cost, accessibility and environmental impact for university waste management.

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